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Informatika fani o'qituvchilarining malakasini oshirishda klasterli yondashuvning o'zni va ahamiyati

Nishonov Akmal Obidovich

Farg'ona viloyati pedagogik mahorat markazi "Amaliy fanlar va axborot texnologiyalari" kafedrasida dotsenti

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada informatika fani o'qituvchilarining malakasini oshirish jarayonida klasterli yondashuvning roli va ahamiyati tahlil etiladi. Klasterli tizim asosida ta'lim berishning afzalliklari, pedagogik samaradorligi va raqamli ta'lim muhitida uning innovatsion xususiyatlari yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, klasterli yondashuvning O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimiga integratsiyalashuvi va uning istiqbollari haqida batafsil ma'lumotlar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: klaster, raqamli pedagogika, malaka oshirish, model, uzluksiz ta'lim, raqamli ta'lim, raqamli kompetensiya, strategiya, innovatsion texnologiya.

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Zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida informatika fani o'qituvchilarining malakasini oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Texnologik taraqqiyotning jadal rivojlanishi informatika o'qituvchilaridan uzluksiz o'z ustida ishlashni va yangi metodikalarni o'zlashtirishni talab qiladi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, klasterli yondashuv asosida malaka oshirishning samaradorligini o'rganish dolzarb masala hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida barcha fan o'qituvchilari kabi informatika o'qituvchilarining ham kasbiy rivojlanishi davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanmoqda. Xususan, klasterli o'qitish tizimi orqali o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirish, ularni innovatsion texnologiyalarga moslashtirish va ularning raqamli kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish strategik vazifalardan biri sifatida belgilanmoqda.

Klasterli yondashuv – bu muayyan sohaga oid o'qituvchilar, ta'lim muassasalari, ilmiy markazlar va texnologik korxonalarni birlashtirish orqali samarali hamkorlik va ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish usulidir. Bu model informatika o'qituvchilarining kasbiy rivojlanishi uchun quyidagi imkoniyatlarni yaratadi:

- Tajriba almashish va innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llash;
- Raqamli ta'lim vositalaridan unumli foydalanish;
- Zamonaviy pedagogik metodlarni o'zlashtirish;

- O‘quvchilarga ilg‘or yondashuvlarni taqdim etish imkoniyati.

Klasterli yondashuv o‘qituvchilar o‘rtasidagi hamkorlikni mustahkamlash bilan bir qatorda, ularning ilmiy faoliyat bilan shug‘ullanishlariga ham zamin yaratadi. Klaster muhitida o‘qituvchilar birgalikda innovatsion o‘quv materiallarini ishlab chiqish, yangi texnologiyalarni tatbiq etish hamda o‘quv jarayonida interaktiv metodlarni qo‘llash imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ladilar.

Informatika o‘qituvchilarining malakasini oshirishda klasterli yondashuvning afzalliklarini quyidagilarda ko‘rishimiz mumkin:

Innovatsion texnologiyalar bilan ishlash imkoniyati – Klasterli yondashuv o‘qituvchilarga so‘nggi dasturiy ta‘minot, sun‘iy intellekt texnologiyalari va boshqa zamonaviy vositalarni o‘rganish imkonini beradi.

Mutaxassislar bilan hamkorlik – O‘qituvchilar ilmiy tadqiqotchilar, dasturchilar va texnologik kompaniyalar vakillari bilan tajriba almashish orqali malakalarini oshiradilar.

Tarmoq ta‘lim muhiti – Klasterlar yordamida masofaviy o‘quv platformalaridan foydalanish va onlayn resurslar orqali o‘qitish samaradorligi oshiriladi.

Ilmiy-amaliy tajriba almashish – Klaster tizimi orqali informatika o‘qituvchilari ilmiy maqolalar va innovatsion loyihalar ustida ishlash imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ladilar.

Raqamli pedagogika – Klasterli yondashuv o‘qituvchilarga zamonaviy raqamli pedagogik metodlarni o‘zlashtirish imkonini beradi, bu esa ta‘lim jarayonining sifatini va samarsdorligini oshiradi.

Moslashuvchan va uzluksiz ta‘lim – Klaster tizimi doirasida informatika o‘qituvchilarining malakasini oshirish uzluksiz davom etadi, bu esa ularning uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanishi doimiyligini ta‘minlaydi.

O‘zbekistonda klasterli yondashuvni informatika o‘qituvchilarining malakasini oshirish tizimiga integratsiya qilish bo‘yicha quyidagi yo‘nalishlarni rivojlantirish maqsadga muvofiq deb hisoblaymiz:

- Pedagoglar uchun maxsus klaster markazlarini tashkil etish;
- Onlayn va an‘anaviy malaka oshirish kurslarini integratsiya qilishsh;
- Ta‘lim muassasalari va IT-kompaniyalar hamkorligini mustahkamlash;
- Ilmiy loyihalar va grant dasturlari orqali informatika o‘qituvchilarining kasbiy rivojlanishini qo‘llab-quvvatlash.

Klasterli yondashuv informatika o'qituvchilarining malakasini oshirishda samarali metodlardan biri bo'lib, uzluksiz kasbiy rivojlanish va innovatsion ta'lim muhitini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalarni o'zlashtirish, metodik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish va ta'lim sifatini oshirish uchun klasterli tizimning qo'llanilishi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kelajakda ushbu modelni yanada kengaytirish va ta'lim tizimiga tatbiq etish zaruriyat hisoblanadi. O'zbekiston sharoitida klasterli yondashuvning joriy etilishi informatika o'qituvchilarining kasbiy mahoratini oshirish bilan birga, ta'lim sifatini oshirishga ham katta hissa qo'shishi kutilmoqda.

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